

Introduction of Society of Automotive Composites Japan

-A new wave of composites for automobile industry-

In the automobile industry, weight saving of car bodies is being tried in order to reduce fuel consumption. Composite materials as represented by CFRP have been expected to be used for car body instead of metal parts. However, there are a lot of new technical problems required for mass-production of car parts with composite materials, the processes to achieve light weight of cars cannot be clear so far. One of the reasons seems that manufacturing processes and required mechanical properties for the composite structural materials have been developed in terms of aerospace applications and these are completely different from that for auto-motive composite.

In order to solve these problems, we established Society of Automotive Composite (SAC) in March 2012 in Japan. Solutions of the problems are that material, molding, and structure for auto-motive composites must be designed just for automotive usage. Therefore, not only automotive companies, but many material makers, molding companies also joined in SAC. The one of main activities are joint research projects between members among industry and academia; such as development of intermediate materials for thermoplastic composite with short fibers or continuous fibers, continuous molding for mass production of FRP, basic research works for interface and interphase, and etc.